

The White and Non-White Women Writers: Spectrum

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A study of select white and women novelists in the North American continent concerns itself with select canadian white writers like Alice Munro and Margaret Atwood and the non-white women writers such as Beatrice Culleton and Lee Maracle. In the perception of the present researcher. Alice Munro and Margaret Atwood are representativ white canadian writers and the other two, Culleton and Maracle, rightly showcase the fears and frustration of the aboriginal minorities in canada. Perhaps a research investigation on the white and non-white writers cannot be conclusive till it addresses the central concerns of these major white and non-white writers.

A glance at the canadian ethnic situation shows that there are two racial groups, the Nativeand White, both creating history and literature of their own. The Native Women leaders and the White women writers are unwilling to group themselves with their white counterparts on the ground that the letters objection to sexism and patriarchy is very limited; the white women’s suffering when compared to that of the Native is almost nothing and therefore the White women’s protest, the Natives think, is not strong enough. The Native writers are concerned with economic survival, ethnic and racial discriminations, as well as sexism. They accuse the mainstream white women’s movement of failing to speak on these issues. The Native woman labour hard in the White woman’s kitchen and takes care of the White household , neglecting her own home: she is the scapegoat for the humiliation which her Native husband suffers in the hand of his white master. This is the sad plight of a Native woman amidst a white majority. The White women are the queens/princesses whereas the Natives, their servants/slaves.

Moving on to the literatures of these women, the Whit canadian women writers recuperate their literary inheritance, though they have no exclusive preoccupation with the traditions of a single country or of a single gender or literary genre. As inheritors whose historical and cultural situation is different from their predecessors they are eclectic in their choices. Margaret Laurence in *The Diviners* acknowledges the British women writer Virginia Woolf and works within the inheritance of modernism at the same time as her protagonist is holding (Howells 20) imaginary conversations with the nineteenth-

century pioneer Catherine Parr Traill, producing within the fiction one novel which is a feminist revision of Shakespeare's *The Tempest* and another based on the legends of the prairie Metis. Canada's multicultural inheritance is written into many of these White writers' fictions with their mixture of genres as well – female gothic, sentimental romance, spy stories, animal revision.

The problems faced by the White Canadians are similar to those faced by any colonial like Australia or New Zealand or, earlier, the United States which has been up against the difficulty of inheriting a mother-tongue together with its traditions and without a powerful infusion of indigenous culture as in Africa, India or the Caribbean – except that for the White Canadians the problems are further complicated by having two mother cultures and two national languages, English and French. How to find a distinctive voice for such a mixed society or to have that voice listened to abroad has always been a crucial difficulty. With Canada it seems to be resolving itself in division, as English-Canadian fiction becomes more widely known in the English-speaking Commonwealth and French-Canadian within the Francophone tradition.

White Canadian literature is currently confronting the same problems of being heard as a 'new voice' while maintaining its 'difference,' with all the instability that this word implies. "Lawrence in 1978 suggested that paradigms of other literatures 'patiently and blatantly' did not enable Canadians to respond to their own literature. While that is true, it is also true that readers outside Canada come to its fiction with exactly those other literary paradigms in their heads. White Canadian distinctiveness may be seen to lie in efforts towards autonomy through displacing the authority of other traditions in order to give a place to what has been traditionally regarded as marginal. As a process of decentralization it is characteristically Canadian. Such shifts of emphasis involve a good deal of ambivalence, which finds its most desperate and negative expression in some Quebecois writers where the weight of European history is seen to lie like a dead hand on the presented, dispossessing the living and draining the life out of them.

In their efforts towards distinctiveness, the White Canadian women writers are aware that they have literary mothers of their own. Contemporary women's writing in Canada is the culmination of a strong feminine literary tradition is double, for while pioneer women wrote about their responses to the wilderness and their experiences as immigrants to Canada, there has also been since the late nineteenth century a movement in the opposite direction with White Canadian women writing about cosmopolitan experiences, like Sara Jeanette Duncan in the 1890s who worked in the United States and in England and (Howells 22) accompanied her husband to India. Their internationalism forms an integral part in the multi-voiced tradition of Canadian women's writing, though it is the national tradition where women have seen themselves in distinctively Canadian conditions.

Only in the nineteenth century did British and European settlers come to Canada in large numbers and to this period belong Susanna Moodie and Catherine Parr Traill, both of whom experienced the challenge of living in the backwoods of Canada and wrote about it for readers back home in England, especially prospective female settlers. Moodie's *Roughing it in the Bush* (1852) is aimed at educating her readers about conditions in the new colony while Traill's *Female Emigrant's Guide* (1854) which was reprinted as *The Canadian Settlers' Guide*. *Roughing it in the Bush* or *The Female Emigrant's Guide* is not fiction. But they shape immigrant experiences in relation to existing fictional models. Moodie, exploiting her responses to sublime scenery and her sense of exile in dark forests, writes in the female gothic mode, while Traill follows a male model of survival in the wilderness likening herself to Defoe's Robinson of piety, practically and determined to name and order and control 'the maze of interminable forest' according to her own imported cultural values. She is the personification of the Victorian Protestant work ethic in its feminine form: "In case of emergency it is folly to fold one's hands.. it is better to be up and doing", a sentence of hers which Margaret Laurence quotes with rueful admiration in *The Diviners*.

Both Moodie and Traill write in the genre of the female Bildungsroman which Maggie Butcher perceives as a distinctive form in commonwealth literature, where women chronicle their emergence from the stereotype of the proper lady into the Canadian pioneer of energetic initiative. Their emphasis is on women's strength in the (Howells 2) absence of men or even in the presence of husbands who are unfit for life in the backwoods. While Carol Shields points to a pattern of reversal of sexual roles in these pioneer narratives, she neglects the doubleness of Victorian women's awareness of the wifely duty that counterbalances their sense of their own power, resulting in strategies of obliqueness in their narratives of the split self which Margaret Atwood perceives as characteristic of the feminine consciousness of Moodie and several other White Canadian women writers.

Anna Jameson uses a kind of metaphorical language to describe her inner quest so that her narrative stands as archetype for many later quests in white Canadian women's fiction. *Suffering and Bear* are the most recent though not the only examples, and how earlier narratives should be included to mark the continuity of this tradition. First come Emily Carr's autobiographical accounts of her journeys as a painter through the forests of British Columbia between 1898 and the 1930s. Here she traces the pattern a visionary quest through the wilderness recording as (Howells) she passes signs of primitive female power in the abandoned Indian totem figures on the west coast. There is also Ethel Wilson's novel *The Swamp Angel* (1954) which begins as a woman's flight from the constraints of an unhappy marriage and becomes wilderness of British Columbia.

This white Canadian female literary tradition gains its strength from women's recognition of their crucial importance in the history of settlement, for while women's work has been largely taken of granted as part of the natural backdrop against which important "man-made" history like railway construction or dominion-provincial occurs, women have never taken it for granted and have redefined their relation to the natural backdrop. Contemporary writers use the same rhetoric of wilderness as their nineteenth-century predecessors, revising their inheritance to accommodate modern versions of similar experiences.

Canada has refused the monolithic stories of British or US imperialism and has been evolving from its marginal position a self-definition based on an ideology of decentralization which recognizes both its difference from outside powers as well as its differences within. The Canadian problem of identity may not be the problem of having no identity but rather of having multiple identities, so that any single national self-image is reductive and always open to revision. This coincidence of similar problems of self-definition in nationalist and feminist ideology would go some way to explain why so much attention is being paid to women writers in Canada at the present time, for their stories seem the natural expression of the insecurity and ambitions of their society and in many ways they provide models for stories of Canadian identity.

Canadianness remains a problematic category in White Canadian women's fiction, where multiple voices and points of view indicate the differences between writers. In *Surfacing*, *The Diviners*, *Lives of Girls and Women*, *Bear*, *Obasan* and *Nights in the Underground*, the geographical signals locate narratives in specific Canadian places, yet the perspectives on Canadian social and cultural values are unmistakably plural.

It is worth looking briefly at women's attitudes to writing as presented in these fictions, many of which have women writers as protagonists. As the novelist Morag Gunn says in *The Diviners*, "a daft profession weaving fabrications.. yet, with typical ambiguity, convinces that fiction was more true than fact. Or that fact was in fact fiction". Morag suggests the multiple function of fiction writing for women as a way of self-assertion out of social or economic constraints. Audrey Thomas's letter-writing heroine in *Latakia* is strongly aware of writing as order in the midst of disorder: "Art is merely the organization of that look chaos". Most of these novels may be read as

revisions of history told from a marginalized feminine perspective, like the history of the Japanese-Canadians in world war II in Joy Kogawa's *Obasan* or the story of one woman who has been dead for eight hundred years in Anne Hebert's where writing becomes a fantastic resurrection. Alice Munro's distinct revisionist tendencies, for as the chronicles of her own life, Del Jordan also writes about the secret lives of earlier generations of women in her fiction a mosaic of alternative female worlds that have been hidden within the living body of social history.

The white writers, Atwood and Mundro write stories where the behavior of the living heart is displayed electronically, and in both primitive fear is the dominant feeling conveyed. Very common feelings among the native writers are their disgust to be born as an Indian, and their hatred perspective towards the White civilization. To escape from the emotionally rotten situation they begin to drink and use drugs. Which they are not able to give up. They start their march against the white with a confidence and a desire to help their people but are suppressed and humiliated by the white who is in high position.

Native people have always suffered the bigotry of the white. Written by non-native writers, Natives histories were always inaccurate. On the other hand, writings by the natives tend to reflect their own voices, coming out from personal experience. More authentic is the writing of a native woman. Campbell in her autobiography very precisely details how her people became squatters on road allowances. The land was ten dollars for a quarter section. Ten acres had to be broken in three years, along with improvements, before title would be granted. Otherwise, Land improvement District authorities confiscated the land. Due to the depression and shortage of fur there was no money to buy the implements to break the land. A few families could have scraped up the money to hire outside. They just did not have the kind of thing inside them that makes farmers. Gradually the homesteads then became squatters on their land and were eventually run off by the new owners.

The native inability to fight the white, their humiliation and their social status have always frustrated the Native. Their humiliation and stressful feelings have driven them to self-destructive behavior like alcohol addiction, drug abuse, neglect of family and children and suicidal attempts. Alcoholism and alcohol related abuse were always a serious social problem among the native people.

In both White and Non-White writers the novelists urge to make thing visible seems to be in conflict with traditional feminine codes of decorum so that the activity of writing itself is problematized in their fictions. Modern women's ambitions are still haunted by an older inhibiting tradition of femininity, and their efforts to write new versions of old stories involve the double process of disestablishment and redefinition of their feminine inheritance(both in life and writing). a concern that addresses the writings of both white and non-white writers.

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